

New dielectric elastomers with improved properties for energy harvesting and actuation

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ABSTRACT

New materials with large value for dielectric constant were obtained by using siloxane and chemically modified lignin. The modified lignin does not act as a stiffening filler material for the siloxane but acts as bulk filler, preserving the softness and low value of Young's modulus specific for silicones. The measured values for dielectric constant compare positively with the ones for previously tested dielectric elastomers based on siloxane rubber or acrylic rubber loaded with ceramic nanoparticles. The new materials use the well-known silicone chemistry and lignin which is available worldwide in large amounts as a by-product of pulp and paper industry, making its manufacturing affordable. The prepared dielectric elastomers were tested for possible applications for wave, wind and kinetic body motion energy harvesting.

Siloxane, lignin, dielectric elastomer, dielectric properties, energy harvesting, composite, mechanical properties.

1. INTRODUCTION

Electro-active polymers (EAPs) are soft active materials, which are capable of fast mechanical deformation when subjected to electrical stimulation¹. Dielectric elastomer actuators (DEA), a subgroup of the family of electroactive polymers, are capable of strains in excess of 200% of initial length or surface², thus being suitable for applications such as artificial muscles, haptic devices, valves and pumps, soft robots, adaptive optics and electric generators.

The actuation strain is determined by the mechanical and electric properties of the material components of the DEA³. While at present the activation voltages for dielectric elastomers are 2–10 kV, if DEAs with increased dielectric constants would be obtained then these materials would be suitable for use in medical implants and would avoid the larger costs associated with high voltage electronics. The material parameters ϵ and Y that govern actuation are functions of the actuation frequency, the stress state and the temperature.

Silicone rubber is tested for actuation or for conversion of kinetic mechanical energy into electrical energy and it is a well-known dielectric elastomer⁴. For such applications where materials must achieve large values for strain, several properties are required: low stiffness (low Young's modulus), high breakdown strength and good values for permittivity⁵. Silicones manifest highly elastic behaviour⁶ and the polarizability of the Si-O bond in polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) is higher than that of organic nonpolar polymers (e.g., polyethylene).

The use of fillers in a polymer matrix is a well-known technique that leads to increased values for the dielectric constant of the material⁷⁻¹⁰ and using fillers also leads to improved mechanical strength properties.

There are available room temperature vulcanization formulations based on low molecular weight polydimethylsiloxane which use reactions of addition, such as hydrosilylation, or the reaction of condensation for obtaining an elastomer matrix with application in actuation. There are also other dielectric elastomer materials available: acrylic VHB foil, polyurethanes, polystyrene/polybutadiene copolymers¹, acrylics and acrylonitrile butadiene rubber (NBR).

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Lignin is a biologically derived polymer with a three-dimensional amorphous aromatic structure and it is easily available and relatively inexpensive¹¹. Most lignin is obtained as a byproduct of the pulp and paper industry (70 million tones annually). Residual lignin constitutes a major environmental problem and it is used as an energy source for pulp industry¹², so researchers are trying to find new applications for it¹³. One possible application for lignin is filler for polymeric materials in order to increase their content of renewable resources¹². With certain polymers, it can give partially or completely biodegradable composites¹³. The chemical structure of lignin presents extensive cross-linking that is a barrier for the incorporation in solid composites, but in optimal blending conditions these crosslinks and hydrogen bonds can be disrupted¹⁴. Therefore lignin represents an opportunity and a challenge for using it in preparing composites with polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) as matrix.

Silicones show characteristics that are paramount for building actuators based on dielectric elastomers: high electric breakdown field strength of more than 50 kV/mm, a low uptake of water due to their hydrophobic character and the ability to function in a broad temperature range from -60 to upwards of 200 °C and the capability to be processed into thin flexible films. Still the polysiloxanes have the drawback of high material costs. In order to surpass this disadvantage two approaches were developed: a) crosslinking the siloxane backbone; b) incorporating powders, many times inorganic ones, as reinforcing and/or bulking fillers for the siloxane matrix.

The purpose of this research is to use chemically modified lignin as filler for the polysiloxane matrix, thus using affordable renewable materials from biomass for obtaining new dielectric elastomers with improved dielectric properties. Lignin was therefore tested as filler for polysiloxane rubber with the purpose of later use in actuation and energy harvesting. Because the chemically modified lignin added to polysiloxane has a hydrophobic character, the resulted materials are considered composites. The films possess enhanced permittivity and the softness and low value of Young's modulus specific for silicones are preserved, as chemically modified lignin does not act as a stiffening filler material for the siloxane.

2.EXPERIMENTAL

2.1.Materials

Polyhydromethylsiloxane- α,ω -trimethylsilyl was prepared in our laboratory and has a Mn=2500, as determined by ¹H NMR measurements.

Octamethylcyclotetrasiloxane, [(CH₃)₂SiO]₄, (D₄), supplied by Fluka AG, with the following characteristics: b.p.= 175 °C; n_D²⁰ = 1.396; d₄²⁰ = 0.955, purity > 99 % (GC), was dried over Na wire and freshly distilled before use.

Purolite CT-175, a styrene-divinylbenzene ion exchanger with -SO₃H groups (4.1 mequiv./g) was dehydrated by azeotrope distillation with toluene and vacuumation at 110 °C/10 mm Hg before use.

Protobind 100SA-140 a lower molecular weight (average Mw=1500) lignin from India obtained from Sarkanda grass, supplied by Granit Recherche Development SA Lausanne, has the following characteristics: 93.59% solids; softening temperature (°C) >200; pH=2.11; aromatic OH=1.75mmole/g; carboxyl=2.12 mmole/g and was used after drying and hydrophobization. The particles sizes, evaluated by SEM, range between 0.5-8µm.

Phenol with m.p. 40.5 °C, d=1.07 g/cm³, purity > 99%, was supplied by Sigma-Aldrich.

Formaldehyde solution 36.5-38% in water with 15% methanol, f.p. = 64 °C was supplied by Sigma-Aldrich.

Sodium sulphite as white powder, purity >98% was supplied by Sigma-Aldrich.

Allyl chloride, H₂C=CHCH₂Cl, AC, supplied by Aldrich, with M = 76.53, b.p. 45 °C, d₄²⁰ = 0.94, purity 98 %, was used as such.

Dimethyl sulfoxide, (CH₃)₂SO, DMSO (Merck) with M = 78.13, m.p. 18.5 °C, d₄²⁰ = 1.1003, purity >99.9 %, was used after drying on calcium hydride and distillation.

Sodium hydroxide, NaOH (Fluka), with M = 40, m.p. 318 °C, d₄²⁰=2.13, purity >98 %, was used after crushing and grinding to fine powder in a mortar and drying in vacuum chamber.

Karstedt's catalyst (KT) Pt₂{[(CH₂=CH)Me₂Si]₂O}₃ (platinum-divinyltetramethyldisiloxane complex in xylene, 2.1-2.4 % platinum) was supplied by ABCR GmbH & Co KG (Germany).

Benzoyl peroxide (BP), 40 wt% blend in dibutyl phthalate (Luperox AFR40) was supplied by Sigma-Aldrich.

2.2.Equipments

Gel permeation chromatography (GPC) measurements for the determination of the molar mass of polydimethylsiloxane were made in CHCl_3 on a PL-EMD 950 Chromatograph-Evaporative Mass Detector. The calibration was performed with polystyrene standards.

Dielectric spectroscopy was performed with Novocontrol "Concept 40" broadband dielectric spectrometer (Hundsangen, Germany). The samples were mounted between gold platens and positioned in the Novocontrol Quatro Cryosystem. The dielectric experiment was carried out keeping the temperature fixed but sweeping the frequency. The temperature was 25 °C and six decades (log scale) of frequency, i.e. 1–100000 Hz, were scanned. Samples having uniform thickness were placed between gold plated round electrodes, the upper electrode having a 20 mm diameter.

The measurements for **Dynamic Vapour Sorption** and **sorption hysteresis** were performed with an IGA sorp Dynamic Vapour Sorption apparatus with the following characteristics: minimum gas pressure 2 bar; resolution of 0.1 μg for 100 mg and sample containers made out of stainless steel micron size mesh. Before sorption measurements, the samples were dried at 25 °C in a flow of dry nitrogen (250 mL/min) until the weight of the sample was in equilibrium at a relative humidity (RH) less than 1%. The measurements were performed with programs involving step increases of 10% for the relative humidity of the flow of nitrogen and recording the mass change for each step. The solid samples were loaded in sample containers made out of stainless steel micron size mesh introduced in the sample chamber. The sample is first dried with a current of dry nitrogen, and then the relative humidity in the sample chamber is increased in 10% steps.

DSC measurements were conducted with a DSC 200 F3 Maia (Netzsch, Germany). About 10 mg of sample was heated in pressed and punched aluminium crucibles at a heating rate of 10 °C·min⁻¹. Nitrogen was used as inert atmosphere at a flow rate of 100 mL min⁻¹. The temperature range for TG-DTG measurements performed with the same instrument was 25–750 °C, using a heating rate of 10 °C·min⁻¹.

SEM images on film surfaces were taken with Electron Microscope (ESEM) type Quanta 200 operating until 30 kV with secondary and backscattering electrons in low or high vacuum mode.

Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectra were recorded in KBr pellets with a Bruker Vertex 70 FTIR spectrometer in transmission mode with collection of 32 scans.

Laboratory oven Venticell 55 (BMT MMM Group, Czech Republic) with 55 liter chamber volume and working temperature from +10 °C over ambient temperature up to 300 °C, with forced air flow in the chamber providing homogeneous temperature profile.

Stress–strain measurements were performed on a TIRA test 2161 apparatus, Maschinenbau GmbH Ravenstein, Germany on dumbbell-shaped cut samples with dimensions of 50x8.5x4 mm. Measurements were run at an extension rate of 20 mm/min, at room temperature. All samples were measured three times and the averages of the obtained values were taken into consideration. The acquired data were processed with MatLab software. Cyclic tensile stress tests were performed on the similar samples between 2 and 100 % strain. The maximum force applied was tensile stress value as determined by previously test. Five stretch–recovery cycles were registered. The stationary time at minimum and maximum applied stress was 5 s.

2.3.Procedure

2.3.1.Preparation of siloxanes and chemical modification of lignin

2.3.1.1. Synthesis of polydimethylmethylhydrogensiloxane- α,ω -trimethylsilyl

The mixture consisting of D_4 with 2.5 wt % Purolite CT-175 and 12.5 wt % polyhydromethylsiloxane- α,ω -trimethylsilyl was stirred at 80-90°C for 3 h in a thermostated reaction vessel equipped with reflux condenser, thermometer and mechanical stirrer. Then, the reaction was stopped by removing the catalyst through filtration. The filtrate was devolatilized in a rotavap at 150°C/10 mm Hg to remove the cyclic and linear low molecular weight compounds. The molar mass of the remained polymer was calculated from ¹H NMR measurements and was determined to be $M_n = 25000$.

2.3.1.2.Synthesis of polydimethylsiloxane- α,ω -diol

The mixture consisting of D_4 with 2.5 wt % Purolite CT-175 and 0.6 wt % water was stirred at 90°C for 5 h in a thermostated reaction vessel equipped with reflux condenser, thermometer and mechanical stirrer. Then, the reaction was stopped by removing the catalyst through filtration. The filtrate was devolatilized in a rotavap at 150°C/10 mm Hg to remove the cyclic and linear low molecular weight compounds¹⁵. The molar mass of the remained polymer was evaluated by GPC measurements and was determined to be $M_n = 150000$.

2.3.1.3.Chemical modification of lignin

The chemical modification of lignin consisted of four steps, each a separate chemical reaction performed in order to introduce in the structure of lignin the desired chemical groups, as described in the subsections below.

2.3.1.3.1. Lignin phenolization reaction

Since lignin has a condensed structure, for depolymerizing and introducing reactive p-hydroxyphenyl groups was used the reaction of phenolation. First a homogeneous mixture of 23 g lignin and 5.1 g phenol was prepared and to this mixture was added 100 ml of 72% sulfuric acid under stirring. After homogenization at room temperature for 20 minutes were added 300 ml of distilled water and it was heated at around 50 °C for 45 minutes. The reaction mixture was neutralized with 5N NaOH and was extracted with ethyl acetate. The organic layer was washed with distilled water and then was concentrated to dry powder using a rotavap. The reaction efficiency was 75%.

2.3.1.3.2. Lignin hydroxymethylation reaction

The hydroxymethylation of lignin was performed by condensation with formaldehyde. A solution of 26 g modified lignin (obtained in subsection 2.3.1.3.1.) in 100 ml 1N NaOH was heated to 80 °C under nitrogen atmosphere in a thermostated reaction vessel equipped with reflux condenser and magnetic stirrer. To this solution was added 4 ml formaldehyde solution. After each hour another 4 ml formaldehyde solution was added and after 4 hours the reaction was stopped by cooling the reaction vessel in an ice bath. The modified lignin was precipitated with 1N HCl solution and the precipitate was centrifuged at 6000 rpm for 10 minutes, washed with distilled water four times and dried in an oven at 55 °C for 12 hours.

2.3.1.3.3. Lignin sulfonation reaction

The sulfonation of the chemically modified lignin (product from subsection 2.3.1.3.2.) was performed in a closed stainless steel reaction vessel lined with Teflon on the inside. To an aqueous dispersion of modified lignin (50 wt%) was added sodium sulphite (2.9 moles/1000 g lignin) and the mixture was loaded in the reaction vessel which was introduced in the laboratory oven at a temperature of 175 °C for 2 h. The reaction product was separated by centrifugation at 6000 rpm for 10 minutes, washed with distilled water four times in order to remove unreacted salt and dried in an oven at 60 °C for 12 hours.

2.3.1.3.4. Lignin allylation reaction

A 8% (w/v) solution of modified lignin in 200 ml DMSO was introduced in a reaction vessel under inert gas (dry nitrogen). To this mixture allyl chloride (100 ml) was introduced in the presence of NaOH powder. The reaction was performed at 70 °C for 5 h. The reaction mixture was poured over distilled water and then washed with chloroform. The fraction with brown flakes was washed with distilled water three times in and the solvent was eliminated from the product using a rotavap. The resulting powder was filtered and allylated lignin was obtained as a light brown powder and it was washed with distilled water on filter paper.

2.3.2. Dielectric elastomer film formation

2.3.2.1. Preparation of films by hydrosilylation

An in house built spin coater with speeds of 300 and 1000 rpm was used to deposit alternating thin layers of polydimethylmethylhydrogensiloxane- α,ω -trimethylsilyl and chemically modified lignin. Each of these two reagents were dissolved to form 15 wt% siloxane solution and respectively 20 wt% lignin solution in chloroform. The measured volume of catalyst for hydrosilylation (KT) was poured in the lignin solution. The speed of the spin coater was varied between the low and high rpm and the two solution reagents were poured continuously one after another. The film deposited on the spin disc was then kept in an oven at 50 °C for 12 h.

Table 1. Composition of the prepared samples

Sample	PDMS-SiH	PDMS-OH	Lignin	KT	BP
S1	-	100	-	-	5
S2	100	-	10	1	-
S3	100	-	20	1	-
S4	100	-	50	1	-
S5	-	100	10	-	5
S6	-	100	20	-	5
S7	-	100	50	-	5

2.3.2.2. Preparation of films by radical condensation

The siloxane polymer was mixed with 5% BP and kept in an electrically heated oven at 180 °C for 0.5 h. Then the pretreated polymer was mixed with the powdered chemically modified lignin in a double roll Yanke-Kunkel laboratory mixer equipped with palettes in Dublex system and cooling mantle. The highly viscous mixture was pressed on a roll press with two rolls, pressed between two aluminum plates and then introduced in the oven for 24 h at 90 °C for elastomer formation.

3.RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The lignin used in reactions is a natural compound – a mixture of different chemical structures and not a pure model compound. Therefore the ¹H NMR was not used to determine the degree of chemical modification of lignin, but FTIR spectral analysis was applied for this purpose. The introduction of phenol groups was proved by the increase of relative intensity of the bands at 1240 cm⁻¹ (for C–O stretch), and at 3440 cm⁻¹ (for O–H stretch). For reacting by hydrosilylation with the SiH groups in polydimethylmethylhydrogensiloxane- α,ω -trimethylsilyl, lignin was subjected to the reaction of allylation. FTIR spectral analysis (Figure 1) was used to verify the occurrence of allylation for the bands specific for the allyl group: the band at 3078-3080 cm⁻¹ for $\nu(=CH_2)$ vibrations, the band at 1645 cm⁻¹ for $\nu(C=C)$ vibrations from allyl group, and bands at 992 and 922 cm⁻¹ for $\delta(C=C)$ ¹⁶.

Figure 1. FTIR spectrum of the lignin products: (a) unmodified dry lignin; (b) chemically modified lignin

One possible application for dielectric elastomers is wave energy harvesting. Therefore it is of interest to test the behaviour of the prepared samples in the presence of water vapours in order to determine the stability of the samples in such conditions. Figure 2 shows the water vapour sorption expressed as the total water uptake per dry sample mass as function of environmental relative humidity.

Figure 2. Sorption/desorption isotherms for the prepared samples (S, sorption; D, desorption):
a) S1; b) S2; c) S3; d) S4; e) S5; f) S6; g) S7

The samples present similar behaviour in controlled-humidity atmosphere, even though two different types of crosslinking reactions were used to prepare the samples. The samples prepared by hydrosilylation (S2, S3, S4) present smaller sorption capacity than the reference sample (S1) since the allyl groups from lignin reacted with SiH groups in siloxane and lead to a crosslinked nonporous surface and also to crystalline surfaces of lignin that were probably formed during the process of spin coating. The samples prepared by radical initiated condensation have larger water vapor sorption capacity since they have a slightly smaller degree of crosslinking (determined from swelling measurements not presented here) and the lignin is condensed in amorphous particles inside the siloxane matrix, thus having a slightly larger water sorption capacity than the crystalline particles formed in the hydrosilylation-based samples. The isotherms correspond to a type III material and show the membranes are nonporous hydrophobic materials with weak interactions between sorbed and sorbing materials. In the kinetic curves (not shown here) the rate of desorption of water vapors is slightly smaller than the sorption rate, leading to appearance of a hysteresis loop, which becomes larger with the increase in the content of lignin.

The DSC data show a peak specific for melting (-37... -40 °C) which has an area smaller than that of the crystallization peak (-70 ... -73 °C), this being an indication that a small amount of crystalline phase develops during the cooling scan. This is a consequence of the presence of lignin particles, both nanometer and micrometer size, intercalated between the siloxane chains and thus lignin hinders the three-dimensional arrangement of PDMS chains needed to develop the crystalline phase. All samples have a smaller area of the melting and crystallization peaks in comparison with the reference sample S1 (pure PDMS), which indicates the introduction of lignin leads to a material with a smaller amount of energy necessary to achieve melting and crystallization. The DSC curves of both hydrosilylation samples S2 – S4 and radical condensation samples S5 – S7 respectively are similar and overlap, suggesting that even a small amount of lignin (10 wt%) has a visible effect on the thermal properties of these materials. Also in Figure 3 it is clear the samples have T_g values in the range -123 ... -124 °C.

Figure 3. DSC results for the tested samples

The SEM images (Figure 4) indicate that native and chemically treated lignin form micrometer size particles. The cryofractured surfaces of spin coated hydrosilylation samples (Figure 4c)...e)) have crystalline microparticles and surfaces developed during spin coating, when in order to achieve a homogeneous surface of the film the solutions of modified lignin and siloxane were poured immediately one after another for different layers, thus leading to a mixture of the two components and not the formation of micrometer size layers.

Figure 4. SEM image of the cryofractured composite films:
a)lignin particles; b) S1; c) S2; d) S3; e) S4; f) S5; g) S6; h) S7

The mechanical testing results (Figure 5 and 6) show a significant decrease of the breaking stress value for composite samples when compared with the reference pure siloxane elastomer (PDMS) and therefore lignin has only a role of

bulking filler, acting as a softener and not as reinforcing filler (in the way that silica and other nanoparticles act for siloxanes). The low value for Young's modulus is beneficial for use in actuation and energy harvesting as it makes it easier to perform these actions by improving the electrical sensibility of the elastomer³:

$$\Delta z/z_0 = p/Y = (1/Y) \cdot \epsilon \cdot \epsilon_0 \cdot E^2 \quad (1)$$

Figure 5. Stress-strain curves for crosslinked samples

Figure 6. Young modulus versus lignin content for the elastomer samples

When chemically modified lignin is introduced in the composition of the films, the value of the dielectric constant increases (Figure 7A) – with more than 100% for the sample S4 compared with reference sample S1. There is a decrease of the relative dielectric constant at higher frequencies ($>10^2$ Hz) because the dipole charges are not capable of rearranging and following the variation of the electrical field. However at low frequencies (of interest for actuation and energy harvesting from waves or from human body kinetic motion) the value of ϵ' is above 4.5 and up to 6.5 for sample S4. The loss factor maintains reduced values when the amount of lignin is 10 or 20 wt% added in the polymer matrix. The relaxation peaks of the siloxane matrix in ϵ'' curves are not present due to extensive crosslinking and the presence of lignin particles, which lead to reduced free volume in the polymer matrix and increased density of polar groups. All samples, including those with high content of lignin (50% - S4 and S7) show an insulator character (Figure 7C) for the range of frequencies studied.

Figure 7. Dielectric spectroscopy results for the tested samples with dielectric constant and dielectric loss values at 25 °C: a) relative dielectric constant; b) dielectric loss factor; c) conductivity, for samples: S1; S2; S3; S4; S5; S6; S7

4.CONCLUSIONS

New composite materials with lignin and siloxanes were prepared using known simple methods from the silicone chemistry. The films have lower values for Young's modulus and thus improved electrical sensibility, a feature useful in actuation and energy harvesting. The elastomer membranes have low values for water sorption, showing a continued hydrophobic behaviour. The dielectric constant of these films increases with the percentage content of lignin added in the formulation, however the dielectric loss for all the frequency range is small only for the membranes with reduced content of lignin (10 and 20 wt% relative to siloxane). All the samples show small conductivity, behaving as insulators, inspite of the presence of lignin which could induce ionic conduction of electrical currents. The hydrophobic character and the increased value of the relative dielectric constant are the premise for using these elastomers for energy harvesting and small-scale actuation.

5.ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Paper dedicated to the 65th anniversary of "Petru Poni" Institute of Macromolecular Chemistry of Romanian Academy, Iasi, Romania.

The work presented in this paper is developed in the context of the project PolyWEC (www.polywec.org, prj.ref. 309139), a FET-Energy project that is partially funded by the 7th Framework Programme of European Community.

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